

The Effect Of Special Exercises Using A Proposed Device In Developing The Speed Of Kinetic Response For Young Basketball Players

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Article Info	Abstract
<i>Article History</i>	<p><i>The purpose of this paper istodesigning a training device for young basketball players and preparing special exercises using the training device to develop the speed of the motor response and identifying the results of the effect of special exercises using the training device in developing the speed of motor response for young basketball players.The researchers used the experimental method for its suitability to the nature of the study. The sample was represented by the players of Al-Hayy Sports Club in basketball, where the number of the sample was (16) players.The researchers chose the community sample by the intentional method, and it was distributed by the simple random method (lottery method) into two groups, the control and the experimental.The duration of the experiment was (8) weeks from (20/5/2021) until (15/7/2021). As for the place of the experiment, it was the closed sports hall in Wasit Governorate. The researchers used the Nelson test for a multi-directional kinetic response. The results were achieved by the scientific methods used, and the researchers concluded that the curriculum that included special exercises effectively affected the performance of the experimental group and the development of the speed of motor response and that the use of modern equipment in the training process had a positive impact on the process of developing the speed of motor response for young basketball players. The exercises from easy to difficult and the use of visual stimuli in training and with regular repetitions had a positive effect in reducing the players' motor response time,The researchers recommend that the trainers pay attention to using a training curriculum that contains special exercises that include the speed of the motor response in their training during the small training unit.The researchers also recommend using the special exercises approach for the speed of the motor response on the clubs for the purpose of benefiting from it in preparing the players during the training phase for the youth basketball category.</i></p>
Received: April 22, 2021	
Accepted: September 30 , 2021	
Keywords :	
Basketball Players, Exercises, Training	
DOI:	
10.5281/zenodo.5542093	

Introduction

Basketball is one of the sports that is widely practiced and occupies a good position, as it has become today very beautiful and wonderful and made those who practice its desire to express its performance perfectly. In which players individually express their abilities in mastering these skills in matches, and the game of basketball requires an integrated preparation for all aspects, physical, skill, psychological and tactical, as it deals with the time element accurately during the real match, and this, in turn, requires the player to improve the speed of his motor response according to the performance requirements, especially in the defensive or offensive side, as the speed of the motor response plays an important role in the performance of basketball skills, as the speed of the match and the change Sudden playing situations require physical and kinetic requirements that always impose on the player to be prepared for various and changing stimuli on the field and to choose the appropriate kinetic response depending on the shape, type and direction of that stimulus, whether it is the opposing player, a colleague or the ball, because all these stimuli require immediate reactions and decisions Quick and accurate, and to improve these requirements, it is necessary to search for means and devices that help the coach in training and developing basketball skills.

The devices and auxiliary tools have a fundamental impact in various sports, including the game of basketball, as we note that those in charge of developing the game have strived to take advanced steps by innovating and developing many methods and training methods and providing trainers, technical cadres, plans, means, supplies and modern devices to advance the game from All aspects, which positively affect the development of the players' abilities to reach the desired goal, which is the strong weapon that the team possesses to control the outcome of matches.Hence the importance of the research in identifying the effect of special exercises using a proposed device to develop the speed of the kinetic response, which contributes to the

development of the defensive skill level of young basketball players in line with the nature of the rapidly changing situations in the conditions of the match.

Research problem:

Raising the sporting level and achieving high achievement in the game of basketball is the main and main goal for all teams, and reaching the highest levels does not come except with the correct and studied scientific method in training, and through the researchers' direct knowledge of most sports teams, they noticed the lack of interest of most coaches in developing the speed of response. The movement during the training units, which created a weakness in the speed of the motor response, which is negatively reflected on the players continuing to raise their skill level and consequently the weakness of their skill effectiveness. There is also a shortcoming in the use of modern training methods to develop these skills. The inclusion of these curricula with training devices and tools aids in the training process of the game of basketball for raising the skill level of the players. Hence, the researchers' idea came to include the exercises used in a training device to develop the speed of the motor response, according to sound scientific foundations to achieve the best results while preserving the health of the players and protecting them from injuries.

Research objective:

- Designing a training device for young basketball players.
- Preparing special exercises using a training device to develop the speed of motor response for young basketball players.
- Identifying the results of the effect of special exercises using a training device in developing the speed of motor response for young basketball players.

Research hypotheses:

- There are statistically significant differences between the tribal and remote tests of the experimental and control groups in the speed of motor response of young basketball players, in favor of the post-tests.
- There are statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the post-tests in the speed of motor response of young basketball players, in favor of the experimental group.

Research fields:

- Human field: Al-Hayy Sports Club basketball players.
- Time field: (28/12/2020) to (2/8/2021)
- Spatial field: Al-Hayy indoor sports hall in Wasit Governorate.

Research methodology and field procedures:

Research Methodology:

Using the random method (using the lottery method)

Community and sample research:

For the purpose of conducting the research and implementing its vocabulary in an accurate scientific manner, the researchers relied on choosing the research community in a deliberate way from the players of Wasit Governorate club teams, the youth category, out of a total of (3) clubs, and the number of players was (62) players. As for the sample, it was selected using the random method (using the lottery method) to select (16) players from the Al-Hay Sports Club players out of (24) players, and this number constituted (66.66%) of the original research community.

The researchers divided the research sample into two groups by lottery as well, which are: -

- **Controlgroup:** the players of Al Hayy Sports Club were chosen, as the training curriculum prepared by the coach was used to develop the variables under study without using the exercises prepared by the researchers with the device used to develop the speed of the motor response. The number of the control group players reached (8) players.
- **Experimental group:** which included the players of Al Hayy Sports Club in basketball, as the exercises prepared by the researchers were used with the introduction of the training device to develop the variables under study. The number of players in the experimental group was (8) players as shows in table (1).

Table (1) shows the total Community of the research according to the clubs to which they belong

No.	name	Number of Players
1	Al Numaniyah Club	20

2	Azizia Club	18
5	Al Hayy club	24
Total		62

Sample homogeneity:

The homogeneity of the research sample was carried out with the variables (length, mass, chronological age, training age) as shown in the following table:

Table (2) shows the homogeneity of the sample in the variables (height, body mass, age, training age)

Variables	Measuring unit	Mean	Std. Deviations	Median	Skew ness
Length	Cm	167	2.16	167.50	0.363
Mass	Kg	62.13	6.55	64.50	0.564
Age	Year	15.25	0.77	15	0.492
training age	Month	4.75	1	5	0.343

Sample equivalence:

The researchers extracted the equivalence between the two groups in order to start one line for both groups as shown in Table (3)

Table (3) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the calculated and tabulated t-value to find equivalence between the research sample for the experimental and control groups.

Variables	Measuring unit	Control		Experimental		T value	level Sig	type Sig
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation			
Kinetic response test	Sec	1402	0.07	1502	0.07	0900	7700	Non sig

Means, devices and tools used in the research:

Data collection methods:

- Arab and foreign references and sources.
- Note.
- Personal interviews.
- Testing and measurement.
- Resolution.

Equipment and tools used:

The two researchers used the following tools: - Height and weight measuring device, a manual stopwatch of a legal basketball court type, a leather measuring tape with a length of (30) m, Japanese-made electronic medical scale, Japanese-made Sony hand-held imaging camera, and (1) pulse watch.

Kinetic Response Speed Device:

Idea Details

The device works to develop the speed of the motor response, as a set of exercises (18) were selected. These exercises are applied to the designed device, where work is done by simulating the movements of the players through the device that works on two levels. The first is a rug containing (6) sensors that connect to the rug in the stereo by special cables, the player, after being directed on the type of exercise, presses these sensors to show the reading on a stereo board that is opposite the player in the form of light signals by lamps located on the stereo and sensors located under each lamp. The researcher has the control panel in order to know whether the player's movements were correct or not at a specific time, and the researcher can reduce the time.

Mechanism of work of the device:

The main program for the work of the device was designed using (C++ language)* where the codes are entered manually (special codes that fit the work of the project in terms of accuracy and efficiency). Approximately 12 entrances and the work will be in the form of a group of (18) exercises. Each group contains (4 different exercises). These various exercises correspond to the work of the device inside the stadium, and it is a training device that was manufactured to develop the speed of the motor response and some defensive skills that are complex with visual stimuli. The idea was discussed by the researcher, the supervisor and the engineer based on previous devices. After setting it up to the device where the device starts working at a known time, and when the researcher changes the program to another program, the device replaces the previous program with a new program, and the researcher can also reduce the time by reprogramming and the benefit of reducing the time is to increase the speed of the player's motor response and increase the frequency in standard time.

Advantages:

- The device is characterized by clarity and ease in applying the exercises as verified through the exploratory experience and the training units of the research sample.
- The device is used with special exercises to develop the speed of the motor response.
- The device is characterized by taking into account safety and security when moving, installing and using it, as well as taking into account individual differences.
- The device is characterized by good local manufacturing, high durability and ease of transportation.
- The device adds an element of excitement and suspense during the players' training unit.

Purpose of the device:

- The speed of the Kinetic response and reaction.
- Keeping the head raised and looking at the opponent without looking at the ball.
- Protect the ball from the opponent.
- The agility of the motor performance of the drum by changing the direction.
- Ease of cutting and penetration into the basket.

Fig. (1)

Shows device shows the speed of the Kinetic response

Components of the device:

- A wooden body, the area of the middle area is 60 x 70 cm. It contains a group of large lamps number (4) and a group of small lamps numbers (7). It also contains two arms. The arms contain a sign showing the player's exit to shooting.

Fig. (2) Shows wooden body

- A sports mat with an area of 100 x 100 cm, containing (6) pressure sensors, connected to the wooden hologram, working to transmit the instructions issued by the player to the hologram

Fig. (3) Shows sports mat

- Key sensors: Six (6) pressed keys. These keys are located on the floor connected to the device.

Fig.(4) shows Key sensors

- Box contains a set of programmable devices.

Fig.(5) shown box contains a set of programmable devices

- Arduino programmable device, through which exercises are programmed and time is controlled.

Fig.(6) shown arduino programmable device

- A device for controlling high voltages (8)

Fig.(7) shown device for controlling high voltages

- Connection cables

- Fig.(8) shown Connection cables

- c++ programs

Fig.(9) shown c++ programs

- Battery (12 volt)

Fig.(10) shown battery (12 volt)

- Programmable computer (laptop)

Fig.(11) Programmable computer (laptop)

Pre-tests:

The researchers conducted tribal tests on the sample members in the Sports Hall on (Thursday) corresponding to (20/5/2021) at exactly four o'clock in the afternoon until six o'clock in the evening before starting the implementation of the proposed exercises curriculum. its actions.

Implementation of exercises for the use of the training device:

After conducting the pre-tests, the researchers implemented the vocabulary of exercises for the experimental group with the help of the assistant trainer using the training device to develop the variables under study from the main section based on some scientific sources in the field of training, knowing that the exercises were presented after their preparation to a group of specialized experts.

- The exercises began on (Thursday, 5/20/2021), and the exercises were completed on (Wednesday), corresponding to 15/7/2021.
- Duration of the proposed training curriculum: 2 months.
- The duration of the training curriculum is weeks (8) weeks.
- Total number of training units (24) training units.
- Number of training units per week (3) training units.
- Weekly training days: (Saturday, Monday, Wednesday)
- The duration of the training of special exercises in one training unit is from (29 to 48.25) minutes within the main section.
- The special exercises in the training units were highly graded according to the ability of the players from easy to difficult.

- Solo and compound exercises, their repetitions, times and rest times were determined.
- The intensity was calculated by means of the pulse, as the player calculates the pulse by using hours to measure the pulse.
- The researchers used the high-intensity interval training method.
- The training modules were applied during the special preparation period.

Post-tests:

After the end of the period allotted for the application of the special exercises, the researchers conducted the post-tests on Thursday, 7/15/2021 at exactly four o'clock in the afternoon until seven o'clock in the evening, in order to measure the level reached by the players and for both the experimental and control groups in order to identify the extent of the impact of the exercises. Special exercises in developing the variables under study and comparing it with the curriculum that was used without the training device in the control group. The researchers were keen to create the same conditions in which the pre-tests for the two groups were conducted.

Statistical methods: The search data was processed through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

Presentation and discussion of results:

Table (4) shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations between the results of the pre and post-tests in the study variables for the experimental group.

Variables	Measuring unit	Pre-test		Post-test		T value	level Sig	type Sig
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation			
Kinetic response test	Sec	1502	0700	9301	1100	12016	0.000	Non sig

Discussing the results of the pre and post-tests for the experimental group:

Through Table (4), we note that the results of the pre and post-tests of the experimental group showed significant differences and differences in favor of the post-test, which indicates a real development in the kinetic response speed variable. The researchers attribute the reason for this development to the effectiveness of the special exercises used with the manufactured device, which It has a positive impact on the movement of the legs, as well as the overlap of these exercises that contain response speed with playing situations and physical abilities related to the skill performance of the members of the research sample, and the exercises directed in terms of gradual size, intensity and comfort helped to adjust the performance of the correct motor paths.

Accordingly, (Issam Abdel-Khaleq) indicates that "when developing the technical condition of the athlete, the increase in the load is gradual in linking the compatibility requirements and the kinetic response test, such as changing the timing of the movement, linking different kinetic elements, changing the initial position, and teaching compound movements"⁽¹⁾,

This confirms the success of the special exercises that were used with the devices in achieving the goal for which they were set, which is the development of a kinetic response test, and this was reflected in the development of skills for the players, since the exercises used by the researchers were built on a scientific basis, in a programmed manner, with effective repetitions and appropriate rest periods, and the gradation in difficulty and observing the differences individually. The two researchers agree with (Faraj Abdel Hamid), who believes that "Special exercises develop neuromuscular coordination and contribute to improving the level of skill proficiency"⁽²⁾.

The conditions facing the player in the basketball game are diverse during the competition and these conditions require several things on the part of the player, especially the need for speed in anticipation, speed in decision-making, speed of reaction and speed of movement, and this is called the speed of the kinetic response.

As for (Ali Sabhan) stated, "The extent of the effect of using the devices for the purpose of developing the speed of the motor response through the performance and repetitions of the exercises in a manner that amounts to being close to the playing conditions, taking into account the change in the exercise, and that giving the player the opportunity to perform the exercises at a slow speed during the first repetitions allows a clear vision This allows the paths to be corrected and thus reduce the time of the kinetic response"⁽³⁾.

Discussing the results of the pre and post-tests for the control group:

Table (5) shows the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the control group between the results of the pre and post-tests.

Variables	Measuring unit	Pre-test		Post-test		T value	level Sig	type Sig
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation			
Kinetic response test	Sec	2014	0007	1102	0700	2079	0200	Non sig

Through Table (5), we note that the results of the pre and post choices of the control group showed slight significant differences, the researcher attributes the reason for this to the lack of focus on the skill aspects and the focus on the fast-moving aspects of performing skills without their accuracy. Since continuing training is not enough to develop the skill side of the player, performing the skills that are characterized by jumping, running and various movements with many repetitions, and during training and playing, is certainly accompanied by a noticeable development for most of the general and private fitness elements without the skill side.

Discussing the results of the post-test for the experimental and control groups:

Table (6) shows the arithmetic means, standard deviations, the calculated (T) value and the result of the differences between the experimental and control groups in the studied variable.

Variables	Measuring unit	Control		Experimental		T value	level Sig	type Sig
		Mean	Standard deviation	Mean	Standard deviation			
Kinetic response test	Sec	1.93	0.11	2.11	0.07	3.62	0.003	Non sig

By presenting and analyzing the results of the post-test for the experimental and control groups, it was found that there are statistically significant differences in the test and in favor of the experimental group. , As well as the comprehensiveness of the training curriculum, the adequacy of the time of the training units, and following the correct steps in the exercises, which led to the superiority of the experimental group. The training curriculum must have a goal that it works to develop, whether it is physical, skill or tactical, and it must be commensurate with the level of the sample and the time allotted to it. (Hamdi and Muhammad) also emphasized, "It is important to give importance to the legalization of the load used in a manner that is commensurate with the level of the trainee individual, the goal of training and the appropriate comfort test" ⁽⁴⁾.

As for the control group, there was less development in the post-tests than the experimental group, due to the lack of use of devices and auxiliary tools that inspire the player to rush, suspense and sufficient repetitions in performing the studied skills. In addition to the lack of training units for the trainer in kinetic response exercises, as well as the link between skills and in a manner similar to the atmosphere of competition, and playing situations, and the lack of interest in such training units during the week within the small training course, as (skilled preparation) "is the process of acquiring, mastering and fixing the technical movements of the activity The athlete smoothly, smoothly and accurately under the conditions and possibilities of different competition situations"⁽⁵⁾.

Conclusions and Recommendations:

Conclusions:

Among the most important findings of the researchers:

- The curriculum that included special exercises effectively affected the performance of the experimental group and the development of the kinetic response speed
- The use of modern equipment in the training process had a positive impact on the process of developing the speed of kinetic response and the performance of basic skills of the players.

Recommendations:

- The need for trainers to pay attention to using a training curriculum that contains special exercises that include the speed of the motor response in their training during the small training unit.
- The researchers recommend using the curriculum of special exercises for the speed of the kinetic response on the clubs for benefiting from it in preparing the players during the training phase for the junior basketball category.
- The necessity of relying on the use of devices in the learning and training process, as the use of devices saves effort and time for the coach and player and gives positive results.
- The necessity of paying attention to the use of modern equipment in the training and educational process.

- Auxiliary devices and tools can be manufactured locally in a manner that is no less effective in achieving their objectives than the tools imported from abroad.

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